

A NEW EFFORT TO ADDRESS SHALLOW GEOTHERMAL ENERGY SUPPLY IN THE BUILT ENVIRONMENT: H2020-PROJECT GEO4CIVHIC

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A major obstacle to decarbonisation in the building sector is the comparably low share of new construction, and the specific problems encountered when supplying RES for heating (and cooling) to existing, and in particular older, buildings. Without a solution to the problem of RES in refurbishment, however, the decarbonisation of the building stock will simply last too long. Shallow geothermal technologies have contributed substantially to decarbonisation in new construction, and also good examples of refurbished buildings using geothermal energy exist. However, for a wider deployment in existing buildings, in particular in the historical ones, the technologies need to be developed further and innovative ideas must be tested and brought to the market.

The full name of the H2020-project to tackle the barriers of shallow geothermal in refurbishment is: “Most Easy, Efficient and Low Cost Geothermal Systems for Retrofitting Civil and Historical Buildings” (short GEO4CIVHIC). The project consortium consists of 19 partners from 10 countries (BE, CH, DE, ES, FR, GR, IR, IT, MT, RO), coordinated by the National Research Council (CNR) from Italy; more details under <http://geo4civhic.eu> .

The project is looking at the two main barriers:

- construction of ground heat exchangers under constrained site conditions

- adaption of heat pumps for supply of temperatures needed for older heating systems and sized for deeply renovated buildings

Development work is done to provide technical solutions for overcoming these barriers with novel drilling tools and enhanced heat pumps. Furthermore, a survey is done to identify and understand all other possible barriers, be they technical or socio-economic, and the project partners work on suggestions for suitable solutions.

A specific emphasis is given to historic buildings, i.e. those dating from before the mid of the 20th century, including listed buildings. The constraints here are even more severe, and in particular the heat pump technology must answer to the characteristics of heating (and cooling) systems that cannot be changed.

Project GEO4CIVHIC, started in April 2018, tackles the main barriers for ground source heat pumps and heat exchangers in existing buildings: Installation of ground heat exchangers under constrained site conditions (like drilling in courtyards, gardens, basements etc.), adapting the heat pumps to supply the temperatures needed for older heating and cooling systems that cannot be easily replaced, realizing small size heat pumps for deep renovations, optimizing dual source heat pumps to reduce overall borehole length, providing engineering and decision support tools and overcoming various non-technical barriers. Starting partly from results of previous projects like Cheap-GSHPs (see more on <http://cheap-gshp.eu/>), and developing new ideas, the project will provide the tools for a larger implementation of shallow geothermal in the built environment, in particular in historical buildings. After practical demonstrations in 3 pilot sites, the solutions will be applied in in four real buildings. In addition, 12 virtual demonstrations (simulation) using real buildings as a basis will show if the solutions found can fulfil the desired objectives, and will help in further optimising the technologies. Eventually, guidelines, education and dissemination will be needed to make the new technologies known and to facilitate their dissemination and application in the market.

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